

A late-medieval ‘lyre-shaped’ buckle from the Durham River Wear Assemblage

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Figure 1 *Obverse and reverse view of ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’.*

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Figure 2 *Illustration of ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’.*

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Accession number Elvet Bridge 4027

Object name Buckle

Number of parts 1

Materials Tin, copper-alloy?

Technique Mould cast with block insertion and tinned

Measurements Weight 11 g, length 51 mm, width of frame 28 mm, width of box plate 16 mm, thickness of box plate 4 mm, thickness of frame 2 mm

Date early 15th century (1390–1420)

Place England, United Kingdom

Acquisition/provenance Discovered in the River Wear near Elvet Bridge, Durham, England, United Kingdom by Gary Bankhead. Gifted to Durham University Museum of Archaeology for use in a learning collection.

Description A large, so-called ‘lyre-shaped’, cast tin, or copper alloy tinned, buckle with hollow integral box plate. Mirrored voluted trefoils decorate the frame. Integral plate is encompassed by a raised border line. Within the border is a raised letter ‘S’, which is surrounded by an incised cross-hatch pattern in the recessed areas. There are two small rivet holes in the hollow plate. Fully intact but missing pin. Corrosion products suggest missing pin was made of iron.

Condition Fully intact, some red corrosion products embedded in recessed area. Missing a possibly iron pin.

Introduction

The function of Artefact ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’ had not previously been identified before this report. Through comparative studies of this artefact, it has been designated as a buckle. Non-invasive X-ray fluorescence (XRF)

analysis was performed on the object to determine its surface elemental composition as tin (Sn). As to what material the buckle's core was cast from, arguments can be made for both tin or a copper-alloy, and so evidence towards both will be given. The parts of and methods used for the artefact's construction will be explored in the context of medieval industries in England. Dating the object to 1390–1420 was concluded by comparison with dated specimens found throughout England that are parallel in shape, decoration, and possibly material. This date was further corroborated by comparison to medieval brass effigies as well as the style of calligraphy used in the raised letter 'S' detail. Additionally, the significance of the decorative elements present in the buckle will be analysed through the lens of early 15th-century English society. Finally, possibilities of who this object may have formerly belonged to will be discussed.

Regional and site context

'Elvet Bridge 4027' was recovered from the River Wear in Durham, England near Elvet Bridge by Gary Bankhead on 19th May, 2012. A possible explanation for this artefact ending up in the river has been given by Egan, who asserts that many medieval dress accessories would have been discarded 'within a generation of their manufacture' if they no longer fit the fashion tastes during that time (1998, 12). Additionally, if this object was of any religious significance its deposition in the River Wear could also possibly be linked to Christian pilgrimage practices (Durham University Archaeology Department 2020).

Durham was an important religious and political site in the medieval period with its towering cathedral and shrine to Saint Cuthbert (Aalen 2006, 158). The city developed around the central cathedral and castle, but the only marketplace remained in the centre of the city in the Bishops' Borough (Aalen 2006, 158). Elvet Bridge, built in AD 1180, connected this market to the 'hinterland to the east ... thus establishing Durham as the crossroads of the country' (Aalen 2006, 158).

Materials

A variety of materials were used to cast buckles during the medieval era in England. Copper, iron, and lead/tin were utilised and blended in varying degrees from 1150–1450; copper and iron being the most common up until the 15th century when lead/tin buckles are found in the larger quantities (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 21). This archaeological data is in line with various charters put forth by the London Girdler's Guild in AD 1321, and again in AD 1344, which essentially outlawed buckles and mounts with 'false work, such as lead, pewter and tin, and other false things' (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 21). Later a statute in AD 1391 relaxed these rules, 'recognising that these metals had been in use for some time, and sought to ease the restrictions', and so buckles and mounts made of non-ferrous white metals

Figure 3 XRF Obverse Reading of 'Elvet Bridge 4027'. © Shelby Navone

Figure 4 XRF Reverse Reading of 'Elvet Bridge 4027'. © Shelby Navone

began to quickly infiltrate the market (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 21). This historical context is important to consider when attempting to determine the metal from which 'Elvet Bridge 4027' is primarily composed.

At first glance the buckle has a dark black appearance with red corrosion elements in the recessed areas. XRF analysis was performed on both the obverse and reverse sides of the buckle and resulted primarily in tin (Sn), *see* Figures 3 and 4. This buckle was also tested in areas that showed signs of wear, which under a microscope revealed traces of an element sparkly gold in colour, and yet the results were still conclusive to tin, *see also* Figure 5. Furthermore, qualitative evidence to a full tin casting can be found in a parallel tin example found in London, *see* Figure 10, which bears the most striking resemblance in style, shape, and decoration, and will be further explored in the section on 'Dating the object: comparative examples'.

What can be known for sure about 'Elvet Bride 4027' is that at a minimum the artefact has a tin coating. This is in line with what was commonplace during the period it is thought to date from, as tin was often used to prevent rusting and give a shine like silver (Egan and

Figure 5 (from top left, clockwise)
 Reverse detail of ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’. © Durham University
 Microscope view of ‘sparkly gold coloured element’. © Shelby Navone
 XRF reverse reading of gold coloured element present on ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’.
 © Shelby Navone

Pritchard 1991, 27). Additionally, a tinned object would have been well equipped to survive the river deposition environment for the last 600 years as tinning can increase the overall durability of an object (Williams 2020). In the case of tinning, a copper-alloy would have been the most likely base material used during this time, so a copper-alloy is also a possible option for what ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’ may have been originally cast from. There is no way to definitively know what material the buckle was cast from without invasive material analysis, since XRF analysis does not penetrate the surface layer of an object.

Components

‘Elvet Bridge 4027’ is fully intact but is missing an (?)iron pin. The various functional attributes of the object have been labeled in the Figure 6 illustration of the buckle and each part’s morphology will be explored in this section.

Figure 6 *Illustration of reverse and interior views of 'Elvet Bride 4027'.*
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Figure 7 *Sketch of London tin example.*
© HMSO

Figure 8 (left to right) *Observe detail view of rivet holes, reverse detail view of rivet holes, and interior view of hollow plate.* © Durham University

Frame

The frame of a buckle is the part through which a leather strap is inserted, adjusted for fit, and fastened. This frame is 'teardrop/pear' shaped. Buckle frames of this morphology are largely referred to as 'lyre-shaped' by many sources (Flynn 2016). Medieval buckle frames come in an array of shapes: round, square, trapezoidal, some with plates, double frames, or other decorative forms. This style of frame on a buckle fits best with the category labelled 'lead/tin frames with integral hollow plate' in Egan and Pritchard's catalogue scheme, as shown in Figure 7 (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 52).

Integral plate

The end of a leather strap would have been inserted and fastened permanently in place with metal rivets into the hollow integral plate. This hollow design could have been adapted from known copper-alloy buckles from the mid-14th to early 15th centuries (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 105). A hollow integral plate was a more secure way of fastening the buckle to a strap than the alternative of wrapping and sewing a strap around a frame and is overall a robust buckle design (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 56). 'Elvet Bridge 4027' has two rivet holes in the hollow plate. Both holes look to be created after the object was cast as the metal folds outward through the reverse side of the buckle as if something was pushed through from the observe side.

Figure 9 Sketch of stone mould. © HMSO

Hole and bar for pin

The central bar would have had a pin made of iron or copper-alloy attached to be used to secure a leather strap to the buckle by feeding it through a hole punched in the leather. The bar on this buckle has red corrosion elements on and around it, possibly indicating the former pin was made of iron. Though it was more common for pins to be made of the same metal as the buckle itself, there is significant evidence for iron pins on copper-alloy buckles, and copper-alloy pins on iron buckles (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 54). Additionally, the XRF findings as seen in Figures 3–5, show peaks of iron (Fe) which could possibly be attributed to a missing iron pin.

Construction

This buckle was most likely cast in one piece using a two-part mould with a block insertion to create the hollow portion of the integral block plate. A stone mould like that in Figure 9 for a buckle of the same category from the same period, could have been used to create ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’.

Dating the object

Comparative examples

A relative date of 1390–1420 has been estimated through parallel material, construction, shape, and decoration of known examples found across England, *see* Figure 10. The category in which this is placed is dated to late 14th, early 15th century and are defined as ‘buckles with integral hollow plates ... cast together with the frame ... [and the] frames are highly decorative’ (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 102). Parallel examples found in copper-alloy, lead, and tin and are all dated to 1390–1420. The tin example mentioned previously as bearing the strongest resemblance to ‘Elvet Bridge 4027’ is illustrated on the bottom center of Figure 10, note the similar voluted trefoils.

Figure 10 *Comparative examples.*

(left to right, top row) **FAKL-BC86A9** (2019), **NARC-E17E95** (2013), **SUR-8B6461** (2017), **SUR-E231BD** (2019), **SOM-77BAE5** (2019). © Portable Antiquities Scheme.

(bottom centre) Sketch of London tin example #479:**SWA81** 1960 (2117) 12. © HMSO

Figure 11 *Matching strap ends*

(left to right) **SF-456D71** (2017), **SF-F906E5** (2018), **SUR-A6DE4B** (2018), **SUR-F7323A** (2019). © Portable Antiquities Scheme

Figure 12 (above left) Drawing of John Cody's strap end. © The London Museum
 (above right) Drawing of Sir Louterell's strap end.
 (right) © The London Museum brass effigy of Sir Andrew Louterell. © Hannan 2012

Brass effigies

The date of 1390–1420 has been based historically on two major pieces of information. The first is that during the 15th century these ornate 'lyre-shaped' buckles were known to almost always be paired with a matching strap end like those seen in Figure 11 (Flynn 2016).

Knowing these strap ends were paired with 'lyre-shaped' buckle frames, scholars determined the dating of this style of buckle based on artistic representations on monumental brass effigies of people wearing 'lyre-shaped' strap ends (Flynn 2016). One such brass belonged to Sir Andrew Louterell/Luttrell who died in AD 1390; his effigy and a drawing of the strap end can be seen in Figure 12 (Ward-Perkins 1940, 267). It is of note that the buckle in this effigy is not lyre-shaped, but square. A second effigy belonging to John Cody/Cory/Corp who died in AD 1391 in Devon also bears a 'lyre-shaped' strap end, illustrated in Figure 12. (Ward-Perkins 1940, 267).

In considering the morphological parallels, it is important to point out that most all the parallel examples are more 'heart-shaped' in their frames while 'Elvet Bridge 4027' has a definite 'teardrop/pear' shape in its frame. No exact parallels were found when compiling this report. This could perhaps indicate a regional preference for this shape.

Figure 13 (from top left, clockwise) Sketch of letter detail on 'Elvet Bridge 4027'.

© Shelby Navone

Alphabet sheet c1386. © Allanheld and Schram 1980

Detail of versals c1400. © Allanheld and Schram 1980

Detail of versals and their decoration c1450. © Allanheld and Schram 1980

Gothic script

Dating is further corroborated through the style of calligraphy shown on the buckle plate. The letter in the centre of the plate most resembles the letter 'S' from the Gothic Textura Quadrata style of calligraphy in use from the 13th to 15th centuries (Drogin 1980, 137). This script had evolved from *Early Gothic* in use during the 11th and 12th century and emphasised angular strokes and compressed lettering (Drogin 1980, 137). With such a long period of popularity, this suggests it was 'approved of and highly readable to the people of its time' (Drogin 1980, 137). Examples of this style of script found in Marc Drogin's *Medieval Calligraphy: Its History and Technique*, shown here in Figure 13, date from the late 14th or early 15th century.

Decorative elements

This section will explore the decorative elements present in the buckle to understand their symbolic and social significance in medieval England.

Trefoils

The voluted trefoils surmounting the frame are unique to this specimen and the tin buckle fragment seen in Figure 10. A trefoil in Christianity is connected symbolically to the Holy Trinity (Liungman 1994, 267). The shape is also commonly found in Gothic church architecture and windows (Liungman 1994, 267). The appearance of trefoils on this buckle could possibly link it to having had religious significance.

Gothic letter ‘S’

The plate of a buckle gave metalworkers an area to add decoration and personalisation. In the comparative examples previously shown in Figure 10, incised lines, letters, crosses, and foliate details were depicted. In trying to understand the possible significance of the letter ‘S’ on the buckle, two reasons for its presence will be posited. The first is that this may be the family surname initial of the owner. Clothing accessories offered people a discreet form of self-expression. With the variety of letters present on the box plates of buckles from this period, it is possible they could represent a family surname initial.

A second interpretation would envisage a religious significance. There are examples of hollow box plates inscribed with the letter ‘m’ which are thought to refer to the Virgin Mary, *see* Figure 15 (Lancum 2017). Additionally, a plate has been found incised with ‘IHC’, which represents the contracted form of the name ‘Jesus’ in Greek, sometimes interchanged with ‘IHS’ (Mitford 1842, 286). ‘IHC/IHS’ has origins which date back to the 3rd century CE and became much more popular in the 12th–15th centuries (Maere 1910). Meaning of the emblem was at times incorrectly interpreted as ‘Jesus Hominum Salvator’, *ie*, ‘*Jesus, the Saviour*’ (Maere 1910). With a history of religious inscriptions on these buckles in mind alongside the interpretation of ‘IHC/IHS’, the letter ‘S’ could possibly refer to the words ‘Salvator’ or ‘Saviour’.

Fine detailing

In comparison to other buckles dubbed ‘lyre-shaped’ this one is particularly ornate and fine in its details. Within the recessed areas of the frame incised cross-hatching is seen in minute detail. This cross-hatching pattern is likely a result of the moulding process.

Figure 14 (left to right) Symbol for the Holy Trinity. © Norton 1994
 Illustration of decorative trefoil detail on 'Elvet Bridge 4027'.
 © Shelby Navone

Figure 15 Left to right: Bronze with a figure of St Christopher with 'M' monogram. © The London Museum 1940
 LANCUM-4A7547 with 'M' monogram. © Portable Antiquities Scheme 2018
 NMS-8FC872 with 'IHC' monogram. © Portable Antiquities Scheme 2018

Final conclusions

Can the detailing, personalisation and ornate nature of this buckle indicate it belonged to someone of higher wealth who could afford to pay for something finer than the simpler parallel examples that survive in the archaeological record? Such an assumption implies that despite the object likely being made of tin, the maker and eventual owner would have still considered the buckle of high value. Tin was a metal that for a period was regarded as a cheap and weaker material hence, as previously mentioned, the London-based Girdler's Guild's attempt to eradicate its use in the construction of buckles with their

charter in 1321, banning the material (Hayward 2012; Egan and Pritchard 1991, 105).

Assigning this buckle to a particular class or social occupation is also difficult as effigy examples linked to this style are from all parts of society: including a knight, a member of the church, and a woodworker. The possible religious significance in the decoration does not help to identify an owner as the church in medieval England was woven into every level of society to varying degrees. Furthermore, assigning this buckle to either a male or female should also be avoided as sufficient evidence to indicate who may have primarily worn this style is lacking. Ultimately, buckles came in many shapes, decorations, and materials during the medieval era as they were an accessory which could 'present a modest opportunity for fashionable expression at virtually every level of society' (Egan and Pritchard 1991, 50). Additional comparative examples in shape, decoration, and style, paired with further analysis of the artefact's metal composition could help to further narrow down what class of society the person was from who may have worn 'Elvet Bridge 4027' before it found its way into the River Wear.

References

- Aalen, F H A and English Heritage, 2006 *England's landscape*. The North-East, London, Collins.
- Drogin, M, 1980 *Medieval Calligraphy: its History and Technique*. Montclair, N J, Allanheld and Schram.
- Durham University Archaeology Department, 2020 'The Durham River Wear Assemblage Project' <https://www.dur.ac.uk/archaeology/research/projects/all/?mode=project&id=622>
- Egan, G, 1998 'Miniature toys of medieval childhood'. *British Archaeology* 35, 10–12.
- Egan, G and Pritchard, F, 1991 *Dress accessories: c.1150 – c.1450*. London, HMSO.
- Flynn, T, 2016 'Buckles'. <https://finds.org.uk/counties/findsrecordingguides/buckles/#Introduction>
- Hayward, M, 2012 'Latten', in *Encyclopedia of Medieval Dress and Textiles*, Edited by Gale Owen-Crocker, Elizabeth Coatsworth, Maria Hayward. http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2213-2139_emdt_COM_415
- Lancum, 2017 'Strap End'. <https://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/770874>
- Liungman, C G, 1994 *Dictionary of symbols*. New York: Norton.
- Maere, R, 1910 "'IHS" The Catholic Encyclopaedia'. <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/07649a.htm>
- Mitford, J, 1842 'An Argument for the Greek Origin of the Monogram IHS'. Read before the Cambridge Camden Society May 25, 1841. *The Gentleman's Magazine: and historical review*, July 1856 – May 1868, 284–6. <https://search-proquest-com.ezphost.dur.ac.uk/pageimage/8491018?accountid=14533>

Ward-Perkins, J B, 1940 *Medieval catalogue*. London, The London Museum.
 Williams, E, 28 January 2020 'RE: Question about tin/tinning on artefact',
 Message to Shelby Navone [Personal Communication].

Figure references

- Drogin, M and Bloomington, Lilly Library (1980, 147) *Detail of versals and their decoration c. 1450* [print] *Medieval calligraphy: its history and technique*, Montclair, N J, Allanheld and Schram.
- Drogin, M. and Cambridge, Magdalene College (1980, 147) *Detail of Versals c. 1400* [print] *Medieval calligraphy: its history and technique*, Montclair, N J, Allanheld and Schram.
- Drogin, M and Oxford, Bodleian Library c 1386 (1980, 150) *Alphabet sheet* [print] *Medieval calligraphy: its history and technique*, Montclair, N J, Allanheld and Schram.
- Egan, G and Pritchard, F, (1991, 52) *Catalogue Scheme* [print] *Dress accessories, c.1150 – c.1450*, London, HMSO.
- Egan, G, and Pritchard, F, (1991:105) *Sketch of London tin example* [print] *Dress accessories, c.1150 – c.1450*, London, HMSO.
- Egan, G, and Pritchard, F, (1991:105) *Sketch of Stone mould* [print] *Dress accessories, c.1150 – c.1450*, London, HMSO.
- Hannan, J, (2012) *Brass effigy of Sir Andrew Louterell*. Available at <https://flic.kr/p/21bv2h9> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Liungman, C G, (1994) *Symbol for the Holy Trinity* [print] *Dictionary of symbols*, paperback ed, New York, Norton.
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2019) **FAKL-BC86A9**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/955287> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2019) **FAKL-BC86A9**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/215844> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2018) **LANCUM-4A7547**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/770874> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2013) **NARC-E17E95**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/476237> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portland Antiquities Scheme (2018) **NMS-8FC872 with 'IHC' monogram**, Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/613021> [Accessed: 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2017) **SF-456D71**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/859740> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2018) **SF-F906E5**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/718152> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2017) **SUR-8B6461**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/253186> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2018) **SUR-A6DE4B**. Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/856889> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2019) **SUR-E231BD**, Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/984356> [Accessed 1 February 2020].

- Portable Antiquities Scheme (2019) *SUR-F7323A*, Available at <http://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/969243> [Accessed 1 February 2020].
- Ward-Perkins, J B, (1940, 267). *Bronze with a figure of St. Christopher with 'M' monogram* [print] Medieval catalogue, London, The London Museum.
- Ward-Perkins, J B, (1940, 267). *Drawing of John Cody's strap end* [print] Medieval catalogue, London: The London Museum.
- Ward-Perkins, J B, (1940, 267). *Drawing of Sir Louterell's strap end* [print] Medieval catalogue., London, The London Museum.